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Open Data in an Analysis of Higher Education in Engineering and Technology in Serbia

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ABSTRACT

The concept of open data is becoming more popular and better recognized in Serbia. The open data offered by the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological development provide a good opportunity to investigate the current state of higher education in Engineering and Technology, as the needed data were generally difficult to obtain outside of the official institutions. In this descriptive study, we look into the number and representation of studies and higher education institutions devoted to Engineering and Technology.

Conference Key Areas: Attractiveness of Engineering Education; Engineering Education Research; Open and Online Engineering Education

Keywords: higher education, open data, study programme, higher education institution

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INTRODUCTION

Proponents of the concept of open data have made some big accomplishments over the past decade. In addition to the rising recognition and popularity of open data, many organizations have adopted this concept and freely given some of their data through open data portals on the Internet. These developments may be especially important for researchers studying educational systems because official data about the educational system of a country were usually “stashed” within an institution and difficult to obtain for an in-depth analysis.

In Serbia, the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological Development (MESTD) has provided some internal data at an open data portal [1]. In this study, we analyse the MESTD open data to better understand the current state of higher education in Serbia with respect to the areas of Engineering and Technology (ET). Our principal data source is a collection of MESTD data sets, of which most relevant for the present study are the data sets about higher education institutions (HEIs) and study programmes organized by these HEIs. In our analysis, we perform the following steps:

- apply statistical methods to create numerical and visual summaries for ET education with respect to study programmes about ET and HEIs that organize such study programmes, including comparisons with other study areas;
- create visualizations that expose discovered patterns with respect to organization and size of ET-oriented HEIs; and
- perform clustering to identify spatial distribution of ET-oriented HEIs.

Specific policies concerning STEM education, of which ET education is an important part, are needed and still developed in numerous countries, including Serbia. To this end, our study may provide some interesting results and observations, which could inspire researchers to conduct similar studies and encourage institutions to be more active in this kind of research.

1 RELATED WORK

Open data are gradually getting more recognition in Serbia. There have already been some attempts at promoting the use of open data in Serbia, mostly through media and sponsored competitions intended for programmers, data scientists, and data enthusiasts in general. An example of a competition aimed at creating software applications based on open data was *Open Data Hakaton* [2], which was held at the end of 2015. During the second quarter of 2016, MESTD organized a competition for students from secondary education and their school mentors. This competition, named *Visualization of Open Data of MESTD* [3], was devoted to visualization of data that MESTD made public at their open data portal [1]. In the last quarter of 2016, the second edition of the *Ministry of Data Challenge* [4] was organized. This competition has a somewhat larger scope. As opposed to the other two competitions, it had an international character since it covered the area of the Western Balkans.

In addition to these competitions, there are also open data portals in Serbia. Since 2015, *Data Centar* [5] has published data on budgets of several municipalities, as well as some data on presidential elections in Serbia. The official portal for open data in Serbia is *Data.gov.rs* [6], which offers data sets from various public institutions. It provides more diverse data sets than Data Centar but it is still being developed and extended. The concept of open data is becoming formally recognized as well. MESTD has included in the draft of the new bill on higher education a requirement for certain official records to be openly available at the Internet web page of MESTD [7].

Stojkov et al. [8] have made a systematic assessment of open data in Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, and Montenegro and concluded that there are initiatives supporting open data but also some shortcomings and challenges still waiting to be addressed by the official institutions. Nonetheless, all these developments indicate that the open data system in Serbia and surrounding countries has been constantly growing over the last few years and moving away from the early stages of adoption.

2 DATA AND METHODS

2.1 Data

Data used in the present study stem from the MESTD. They are mostly from the collection available at the MESTD open data portal, with some smaller portions extracted from the official web page of MESTD. However, MESTD offers data in the form of separate data tables, which may lengthen the process of data preparation within data analysis. For this reason, in a separate study [9], we integrated MESTD data tables that are related to higher education and science into a single data store, which is used as a data source in the present study.

Within the used collection of open data, most important data for our study are about HEIs and study programmes. There are records about 1899 study programmes at HEIs in Serbia in 2016, which include information such as name, responsible institution, study field, degree type, duration, area, tuition fees, and student count by study year, funding mode, and student origin. Available data about HEIs comprise 254 records, which include information such as institution name, university name (if applicable), institution type, address, phone number, address of the official web page, and location in the form of GPS coordinates. The complete list of all the tables and all the contained attributes is available as a result of our data integration study [9].

2.2 Methods

The present study is descriptive as we analyse the available data about higher education in Serbia that were collected by MESTD. It has exploratory character since we try to learn more about higher education in ET in Serbia by freely inspecting data without particular hypotheses. However, the results of this analysis, which may be regarded as exploratory data analysis, could serve in generation of new research questions.

Within the open data of MESTD, a study programme is classified as belonging to one of the following six study fields:

- ART – Art,
- TTS – Technical and Technological Sciences (TTS),
- NSM – Natural Sciences and Mathematics,
- MS – Medical Sciences,
- IMTTS – Interdisciplinary, Multidisciplinary, Transdisciplinary (IMT), and Two-Subject Studies, and
- SSH – Social Sciences and Humanities.

For the purpose of data analysis within the present study, we regarded a study programme as ET-oriented if it has been classified by MESTD to be in the field of TTS. In the similar manner, we considered an HEI to be ET-oriented if the majority of the study programmes it organizes are ET-oriented. The field of IMTTS may include some studies connected to ET, but since the available data do not support

identification of ET share in a study programme, we did not consider IMTTS to be related to ET.

We analysed the representation of ET-oriented study programmes within the whole body of study programmes. We also looked into the representation of students enrolled in ET-oriented study programmes and how the shares of different funding modes of students differ across study fields. The funding modes recognized by MESTD in their open data comprise budget-funded (BF) students, self-funded domestic (SFD) students, and self-funded foreign (SFF) students.

Additional analysis was performed to identify which HEIs are ET-oriented, how they are grouped into universities, and how they are geographically grouped, i.e., which cities are centres of ET studies in Serbia.

The data analysis was conducted using R [10], an environment for statistical computing, and various R packages from the official R repository (dismo, geosphere, png, raster, rgdal rgeos, sp, and treemap). The map of Serbia was prepared based on spatial data from the GADM database of administrative areas [11].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Study programmes

Within the collection of MESTD open data, there are 1899 study programmes, including all study fields and degree types. These study programmes are organized by 175 different HEIs. The distribution of study programmes across the six study fields is given in Figure 1. In Serbia, the largest group of study programmes is offered in the SSH field, closely followed by the study programmes in the TTS field, i.e., ET-oriented study programmes. There are 609 ET-oriented study programmes, i.e., 32.1% of all study programmes are ET-oriented. The study programmes in the other four study areas constitute approximately one third of all study programmes. There is a great imbalance in study field share in favour of SSH and TTS studies.

Fig. 1. Distribution of study programmes by study field

In total, there are 247402 students enrolled at HEIs in Serbia. The distribution of enrolled students across different study fields is shown in Figure 2. As it could be expected based on the distribution of study programmes, the majority of students are enrolled in SSH study programmes, i.e., 110732 students. There are 75749 ET students, i.e., they make up 30.6% of all students, which is in line with the share of ET-oriented study programmes. However, the distribution of enrolled students among

the other study areas does not completely follow the distribution of study programmes by study area. The differences in shares of students for the MS, NSM, IMTTS, and ART fields are greater than it could be expected based on the distribution of study programmes. This might be a consequence of varying enrolling policies between different study areas, e.g., fewer students get enrolled per study programme in the ART field than in any other study field.

Fig. 2. Distribution of enrolled students by study field

The distribution of enrolled students within a study field with respect to funding mode is presented in Table 1. The share of ET students in the group of budget-funded students is 34.9%, which is more than expected. More than half of ET students are budget-funded, namely 52.8%. This is the best ratio of budget-funded students in a study field, except for the ART studies, which typically have a considerably smaller number of students. This high rate of budget-funded students in ET studies, which feature such a high share of students in the total student population, is a strong pattern showing that ET-oriented studies have a major funding support from MESTD and the government. This is also noticeable in the high ratio of 1.12 budget-funded students per one self-funded student.

Table 1. Distribution of enrolled students within a study field by funding mode

Study field	BF		SFD		SFF		BF / (SFD+SFF)
	Total	%	Total	%	Total	%	
SSH	44157	39.88	66263	59.84	312	0.28	0.66
TTS	39999	52.80	35426	46.77	324	0.43	1.12
MS	13690	50.10	12969	47.46	667	2.44	1.00
NSM	8773	48.18	9317	51.16	120	0.66	0.93
IMTTS	4780	44.69	5832	54.52	85	0.79	0.81
ART	3160	67.41	1509	32.19	19	0.41	2.07

3.2 Higher education institutions

Out of 175 HEIs that organize at least one study programme, there are 56 ET-oriented HEIs. If the institutions that offer at least one ET-oriented study programme are included in this count, there are 62 HEIs that offer ET education to students. The six institutions that have ET-oriented studies but are not predominantly devoted to ET

comprise three higher schools, two rectorates, and one faculty. The distribution of ET students by ET-oriented HEIs is depicted using a treemap visualization shown in Figure 3. The institutions are grouped by the university of which they are part, except for higher schools, which function independently. The institution with most ET students is the Faculty of Technical Sciences of the University of Novi Sad, which has 11824 ET students. The next five largest ET-oriented HEIs are all part of the University of Belgrade.

Fig. 3. Treemap for ET-oriented HEIs based on the number of students enrolled in ET-oriented study programmes

A map of higher education centres for ET is shown in Figure 4. All ET-oriented HEIs except two small HEIs of unknown location were clustered by proximity using hierarchical clustering. The map includes the name of the city, or multiple cities close to each other, and the number of ET students enrolled at ET-oriented HEIs there.

4 SUMMARY

In the Strategy on Scientific and Technological Development [12], the Government of Serbia focuses on increasing the share of students studying Natural Sciences and Engineering. Although the analysed data do not provide records over several consecutive years, the presented results suggest that ET studies play a very important part in the higher education system of Serbia. With respect to the number of available study programmes and the number of enrolled students, the ET field is second only to the field of Social Sciences and Humanities. Moreover, with respect to the share of budget-funded students, it surpasses all the other fields except the field of Art, which traditionally offers only a low number of positions for students.

Fig. 4. Centres for higher education in ET in Serbia

As expected, the main centres for higher education in ET are the largest cities, namely Belgrade, Novi Sad, and Niš. If population levels are taken into consideration, then Novi Sad in particular has a prominent role in ET education. The special status of Novi Sad in this regard may be primarily attributed to the Faculty of Technical Science of the University of Novi Sad, which is the largest ET-oriented HEI in Serbia. On the other hand, throughout Central Serbia, there are smaller higher education centres offering ET studies, many of which are organized by higher schools.

The MESTD open data present a unique opportunity to analyse data previously reserved primarily for MESTD and the Statistical Office of Serbia. The veracity and completeness of analysed data are closely tied with the usefulness of the results. However, given the official character of published records and their extensive coverage, there should be good confidence in the findings. Our plan for future research is to analyse also the state of science and research activity in Serbia.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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REFERENCES

- [1] Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological Development of Serbia (n.d.), Open data (in Serbian), Available: <http://opendata.mpn.gov.rs/> (July 14, 2017)
- [2] Hakaton.rs (n.d.), Hakaton: A project of the non-profit organization SEE ICT (in Serbian), Available: <http://hakaton.rs/> (July 14, 2017)
- [3] Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological Development of Serbia (n.d.), Prize competition for school programming teams (in Serbian), Available: <http://opendata.mpn.gov.rs/konkurs/konkurs.html> (July 14, 2017)
- [4] Ministry of Data (n.d.), What is the Ministry of Data challenge?, Available: <http://www.ministryofdata.info/> (July 14, 2017)
- [5] Data Centar (n.d.), Welcome to Data Centar, Available: <http://datacentar.io/en> (July 14, 2017)
- [6] Open Data (n.d.), #OPENDATA: Open possibilities for every one of us (in Serbian), Available: <https://data.gov.rs/sr/> (July 14, 2017)
- [7] Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological Development of Serbia (n.d.), Public call for participation in the discussion about the Draft Higher Education Bill (in Serbian), Available: [http://www.mpn.gov.rs/javni-poziv-za-ucisce-u-javnoj-raspravi-o-nacrtu-zakona-o-visokom-obrazovanju/](http://www.mpn.gov.rs/javni-poziv-za-ucesce-u-javnoj-raspravi-o-nacrtu-zakona-o-visokom-obrazovanju/) (July 14, 2017)
- [8] Stojkov, M., Gostojić, S., Sladić, G., Marković, M. and Milosavljević, B. (2016), Open government data in Western Balkans: Assessment and challenges, Proc. of the 6th International Conference on Information Society and Technology (ICIST 2016), Zdravković, M., Trajanović, M. and Konjović, Z. (Eds.), Kopaonik, Serbia, pp. 58-63.
- [9] Ivančević, V., Ivković, V. and Luković, I. (2017), Integrating open data on higher education and science in Serbia, Proc. of the 8th PSU-UNS International Conference on Engineering and Technology (ICET-2017), Katić, V. (Ed.), Novi Sad, Serbia, Paper No. T4-1.1, pp. 1-5.
- [10] R (n.d.), The R project for statistical computing, Available: <https://www.r-project.org/> (July 14, 2017)
- [11] GADM (n.d.), GADM database of Global Administrative Areas, Available: <http://www.gadm.org/> (July 14, 2017)
- [12] Ministry of Education, Science, and Technological Development of Serbia (n.d.), Strategy on scientific and technological development of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2016 – 2020 – Research for innovation (in Serbian), Available: <http://www.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/STRATEGIJA-naucnog-i-tehnoloskog-razvoja-RS-za-period-2016-2020..pdf> (July 14, 2017)